

SPEECH TECHNIQUE IS A BEAUTIFUL SPEAKING ART.THE CONCEPT OF SPEECH TECHNIQUE.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6528684>

Rakhimova Charoskon Odiljonovna

*Student of Presidential Scholar of the
State World Languages University of Uzbekistan*

Ne'matullayeva Nodirabegim Nodirovna

Student of Uzbek State World Languages University

Annotation: *Beautiful and attractive speaking are important for everyone. Because first of all beautiful speech attracts people, on the other hand, in any field, of course, speech techniques are very significant. Even in ordinary speech, if the task of making a powerful impact is not set, not only the content of the information but also the tone of the speaker's speech will be perceived. It is important to hear your voice from the outside in order to improve your speaking skills. Therefore, in this article, I firstly talked about what is beautiful attractive speech, rethoric, as well as its techniques.*

Keywords: *Attractive speech, rethoric, communication, language logic, fluently speaking, glossophobia, ordinary speech, language and speech culture, sound, tembr, intonation, volume and range development, speech techniques, pre-show, impression*

In his speech, President Islam Karimov stressed the importance of learning foreign languages. Today, it is difficult to understand and justify an expert who is completely independent, fluent, beautiful and concise in his native language, especially, those who sit in the chair of the leader. Language is a means of communication, and speech is the process of communication. Speech activity is the process by which a person uses language to assimilate socio-historical experiences and pass them on to future generations or to establish communication or develop their own actions. The more beautiful and meaningful the speech, the more appealing it will be. People have been interested in this issue since ancient times. Theoretical foundations of speech culture were established in ancient Greece and Rome. Public speaking has risen to the level of art. They had to master the art of public speaking to become mature people. In 335, Aristotle's Rhetoric was created. Cicero's "On the Speaker", "The Speaker", and Mark Fabius Quintilian's "On the Preparation of the Speaker" are also about the art of public speaking. In the East, including Movarounnahr, preaching is very important. As the art of public speaking grows, so do the demands placed on speech. The great scholars Beruni, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Mahmud Kashkari, Zamakhshari, Kaikovus and

others created works on language logic and rhetoric. In the Nightmare, Kaikovus encouraged his children to speak kindly, politely, appreciately and not in vain. "When you speak in public, let your word be beautiful, let the word be accepted by the people. Let the people know that you have reached a high level with words, because they know a person's rank through words", the scholar wrote. He also says that the speaker should know the language of the people, their thoughts and psyche.

Yusuf Khos Khojib's "Qutadg'u Bilig" also contains valuable insights into language etiquette and oratory culture. He talks about being short, about adding as much meaning to words as possible. The language enhances a person's dignity, or it can be used to degrade a person, says the author

Alisher Navai is a flag bearer of beautiful speech in Turkish. He laid the foundation of Uzbek literary language with his work. It showed the richness of the language. Navai's works "Muhokamat ul-lug'atayn" "Mahbub ul-qulub", "Nazm ul-javohir" are beautiful examples of Uzbek speech, but also contributed to its development. "Mahbub ul-qulub" provides important insights into the importance

of language, its use, and the culture of speech. A number of post-Navai writers and scholars, including Jadid intellectuals, have expressed their views on language and speech, language and speech culture.

Glossophobia, the fear of speaking, is common. Most people are afraid of expressing their thoughts if there is a larger audience in front of them. They tend to forget something while lecturing on an issue and then get nervous. That leaves a bad impression on the attendees, no doubt. However, being nervous and forgetting things is human. It can happen to even professional speakers. But the professionals know how to tackle nervous and awkward situations.

Even in ordinary speech, only if the task of making a strong impact is not set not only the content of the information but also the tone of the speaker's speech is perceived speech. It is important to hear your voice from outside to improve your technique. Here it is the tape recorder is an invaluable aid to teachers. Different types of verbal exposure you need to record it on a magnetic tape a few times and listen to it to make sure it is from time to time the tone of voice becomes clearer and more relevant to the task at hand come and perfectly express the individual characteristics of the speaker.

Language and speech culture

The culture of a language includes its vocabulary, syntactic development and level of enrichment, the sharpness of the meanings of the words, the variety of the

tone of speech is understood. Of speech culture is the sum and system of its communicative qualities, which are the linguistic culture in linguistic activity. The acquisition of the linguistic potential of a language takes place in two stages.

Step 1: language tools consists of language knowing. The meaning and function of the language tools used in listening to this speech appears to understand. Exactly, the listener listens and understands what is being read. Such a person understands the speech of others. But his speech is full of language deprived, destitute.

Step 2 deepens the understanding of most of the possibilities offered by the language system conversion to speech speed. The speech of the person who has achieved this is fluent, rich, figurative, appropriate. Continuous exercise on the means of speech realized in step 1, paying constant attention to memorizing them turns these possibilities into speech speed.

Reading is the student's communication with the author and images through written speech. The reader becomes aware of the events reflected in the written speech, under the influence of them there is a change in behaviour. Reading is the most important way to learn. One achieves spiritual maturity through reading.

Speech etiquette is the main criterion that determines a person's general morality. Man's manners are first and foremost reflected in his speech. What is speech etiquette? When it comes to speech etiquette the message that needs to be conveyed, while respecting the listener, is literary to his or her liking delivery with normative expressions is understood. To the listener of any ugly news can be delivered safely. For this, the language of speech the norms of literary language are perfect should know. Gentle, pleasant, well-spoken speech does not just happen. For this result, conscious exercise from a young age, mastering the vocabulary of the language, speech in this regard is exemplary by imitating people, by learning from them.

Speech techniques include speech production, articulation, diction, intonation, facial expressions, and science in the field of other elements. Certain professions should study this science for a lifetime. Their task is to make the speech technique correct, beautiful and understandable.

Sound

Pleasant voice is one of the main indicators of correct speech. The sound is also suitable for training comes and can deliver it. Everyone has to control the power of the voice depending on the situation can learn to raise or lower, to hold emotions, to be calm, and suffice it to say with measurement. A healthy throat is an important factor in quitting smoking need.

Tembr

The next indicator is the timbre of the voice. In this case, the main thing is not to overdo it, because overdoing it except low or loud sound is considered false. To deal with the timbre of the voice the most important moment is to breathe and work with the diaphragm.

Intonation

Pay attention to intonation and correct pronunciation, place stress correctly in words, and make sense it is important to pause. This allows you to hold your breath, ordering the next speech correctly and attract the attention of the audience.

Volume and range development:

- Select a poetic text of eight or more lines and select it. Start pronouncing so that at the beginning of the line is your range the weak level drops and in each row it grows slowly, the final reaches the limit

- Once you have done this exercise, start at the border and do your own end with a low range of your voice.

- Based on the results of a successful performance, the lines of the poetic story multiply.

Speech Techniques

Speech is the ultimate cultural fingerprint. After you speak a single sentence, listeners will come to some quick conclusions about you, possibly including the following:

- What country or region you grew up in.
- Whether English was your first language.
- What your educational level is.
- How smart you are.
- Whether you are an introvert or extrovert.

I'm not saying that listeners' conclusions will be accurate and I'm not saying that it is right for people to make snap judgements about you, but I am saying that this is reality. So, turn this reality into your ally.

Something to Work At

You can improve your speaking just as surely as you can improve your writing. Speech is something you have to work at. You work at it by practicing-- both by yourself and in front of others. When others give you useful feedback on speaking, take it as a gift and integrate their suggestions. If you have the chance, working with a speech coach can be quite valuable. I used to ask students which actor's voice they most respected. Since every class immediately chose

James Earl Jones, I'll cut to the chase. James Earl Jones was not born with that golden voice. In fact, as a boy, he had a severe stutter. The stutter distressed him so much that he stopped speaking. It was only through a series of gifted teachers that he overcame the stutter and developed his majestic voice. The last interview I read indicated that he was still working with a speech teacher.

The Basics

- Speak loudly enough to be heard. Project your voice.
- Speak clearly. Enunciate the final syllable of each word--make sure you catch all the consonants. [Have class stand up and say: "The Trans-Siberian Railroad Does Not Stop in Paris."]
- Make eye contact. If you're really scared, feel free to stare just a little above their eyes.
- Stand up straight; don't slouch. Square your shoulders.
- Avoid Entrancing Your Audience

Your listeners have a very short attention span. You are at war to keep their focus. To win the battle, avoid entrancing your audience. Just about any form of repetition can put intelligent audience members into a very mild trance. Seek discontinuities!

To avoid repetition, alter:

- The speed of your delivery. Slow down once in a while and speed up once in a while.
- The volume of your delivery. You can emphasize points by raising your voice or by lowering your voice.
- The body motions of your delivery. Never rock rhythmically. Never move your hands rhythmically. Feel free to walk around, particularly if you are using a wireless microphone.

In addition, if you must hold an audience's attention for a long time, try to change topics every 15 minutes or so.

Mesmerize. Don't entrance.

Learn from Entertainers

You don't have to be Jay Leno while giving a speech. Nevertheless, technical speakers wishing to enhance their success rate should learn the secrets of professional entertainers. You should treat listeners as an audience whose attention you must hold. You must learn to engage your audience. If you don't have their attention, your message will be lost.

As with any form of communication, you must know your audience. If the forum at which you are speaking is very conservative, then beware of many of

these suggestions. If, however, the forum is somewhat more casual, then take these suggestions seriously and emerge as the speaker that gets invited back.

Provide a Pre-Show

A pre-show is, not surprisingly, the information that precedes the show. All forms of professional entertainment provide a pre-show to build an audience and to build excitement. For example:

- Movies provide trailers.
- Theatres provide playbills.
- Television provides little teasers (an "All New Simpsons" this Sunday night).

Technical speakers should also provide pre-show. Your audience should anticipate your speech. You should build a little buzz for your speech ahead of time. Perhaps you'll have someone distribute interesting handouts related to your presentation a few minutes before you speak. Perhaps these handouts will suggest something intriguing or puzzling.

Get the audience anticipating your speech before you say your first word.

Be Confident

Always believe that you are speaking about the most fascinating topic in the world. If you are talking about slug migration, then believe that everyone in your audience will be fascinated by slug migration.

An audience can smell the lack of confidence from a mile away.

Make a Good First Impression

As with many forms of communication, the audience makes very quick assessments. If you win over the audience at the beginning, things will roll your way. If you lose the audience at the beginning, it is very hard to regain them.

To make a good first impression, just:

- Smile.
- Be confident.
- Open with a (good) joke.
- To present serious business, walk faster to the podium.

Be Funny

If you are reasonably comfortable telling a joke, then open with a joke relevant to your topic. Likewise, it is wise to end with a relevant joke. Most members of your audience will appreciate this effort tremendously. Again, you don't have to be a professional comedian to pull this off.

By the way, spontaneous remarks almost always work better than prepared ones. So, prepare some spontaneity.

If you are clumsy with humor, don't attempt this.

A simple formula: start with a joke, end with a joke, show good graphics in between.

Deliver a Grand Finale

Good shows end with something big. Try to pull off a surprise just near the end. Better yet, promise your listeners something exciting, but don't deliver on it until the end of the presentation.

Body Language

Here are a few general suggestions:

- Stand up straight but not too stiffly. Lean forward slightly. Don't slouch.
- Project confidence by keeping your body expressions expansive.
- Move around a little. You can even move into the audience from time to time.
- Move your hands a bit. Just don't flap your hands enough to go into flight.

As you give speeches in this class, audience members will provide very useful feedback on your body language. Some of the feedback will amaze you. ("I was doing that?")

Want some help on body language? Watch tv with the sound off. Watch David Letterman or Jay Leno and see how they invite you in through fairly relaxed body movements. Watch politicians try to convince you of their point of view through persuasive hand motions. Watch news reporters and see how their posture conveys gravity or intensity.

Note that some people in your audience are very attuned to body language and will pick up on all sorts of clues from it. Some will be trying to detect whether you are telling the truth, or at least, whether you believe in what you are saying. So, tell the truth and believe in what you are saying.

Dress for Success

Some will attend strongly to what you are wearing; others won't even notice. For those in the audience that do care about your clothes, dress wisely. Ask someone for help in this area (preferably someone without any MIT affiliation).

REFERENCES:

1. Art of public speaking: tips and tricks to mastering your communication skills. Webinar June 17 , 2021
2. 7 tips of beautiful speaking. July 8, 2019
3. How to develop clear speech. November 5, 2021

4. Literary techniques for your speech, with examples analyzed. March 2, 2021
5. 15 techniques to master speech. March 15, 2022
6. The language of persuasion: Techniques in Speeches. January 30, 2021